

Analysing Global Policy Responses to COVID-19: An Agent-based model to explore the stringency in policies

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Summary

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2019 prompted nations worldwide to implement various strategies to curb the rapid spread of the virus. Our analysis relies on data from Our World in Data to discern differences in the stringency index embraced by various countries. To further investigate, we categorised nations into three groups depending on the extent of measures implemented: no lockdown, partial lockdown, and full lockdown. In this regard, we developed an agent-based model to explore into the intricacies of policy adoption and its efficacy among countries worldwide.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19; Policy diffusion; Agent-based Model; Stringency index; Homogeneity in policy adoption

1. Introduction

Numerous global challenges emphasise the importance to undertake rapid decisions at international level. One recent example of rapid and uniform international policy coordination occurred in response to the COVID-19 pandemic through the implementation of lockdowns. The driving factors related to lockdown has received relatively less attention. Sebhatu et al. (2020), a notable study quantifying the diffusion of COVID-19 interventions, highlighted the level of consistency in the adoption of lockdown measures across vastly diverse countries within a short timeframe. Despite some quantitative analyses on the factors influencing the policies, there is a notable gap in exploring the computational and simulation aspects of the swift changes in the diffusion of COVID-19 policies. Unlike quantitative models, simulation models can enable the researchers to observe how diffusion of policies vary under different conditions, providing insights into the underlying mechanisms driving decisions in uncertain situations. In this regard, an agent-based modeling (ABM) approach can enable the researchers to explore deeper into the mechanisms of diffusion to generalise the homogeneous decisions adopted by heterogeneous countries across the globe.

1.1. Relevance of Agent-based models in studying policy diffusion

ABMs, providing a versatile and powerful framework to understand complex systems, often leverage social network structures as the fundamental framework for simulating the spread of ideas, innovations, or cultural practices (Kiesling et al., 2012). Moreover, ABMs have been extensively applied to study the transmission dynamics of the COVID-19 virus. In the context of the pandemic, these models simulate the interactions among individuals within populations, considering factors like mobility, contact patterns, and transmission rates (Cuevas, 2020; Kai et al., 2020; Kerr et al., 2021; Lorig, Johansson, and Davidsson, 2021). By incorporating the effects of policy interventions, such as lockdowns, social distancing measures, and vaccination campaigns, ABMs can offer valuable insights into how these interventions impact the spread of the virus over time. In this regard, this study proposes an agent-based model to explore the dynamics of policy adoption and their effectiveness among countries across the globe, drawing on Sebhatu et al's (2020) research that emphasises the homogeneity in COVID-19 policy adoption.

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1.2. Need for stringency in policy adoption

Sebhatu et al. (2020) attributed the homogeneity in policy interventions to a process of imitation. It must be noted that the study formulated the semiparametric Cox proportional event history model by using a binary adoption variable as the dependent variable capturing the occurrence of the event of interest. However, their findings indicated no causal effect of COVID cases on policy adoption, prompting the need to explore the stringency in policy adoption and assess any direct implications of COVID cases on the decision-making process for stringent measures, given the diversity of policies adopted by countries beyond singular interventions. Therefore, our investigation utilises data from Our World in Data (Mathieu et al., 2020) to identify variations in the stringency index adopted by different countries.

2. Methodology

2.1. Categorising policy based on “stringency index”

Our World in Data (Mathieu et al., 2020) gathered information on various policy measures adopted to tackle COVID-19 such as, “school closures”, “workplace closures”, “face coverings”, “internal movement restrictions”, “international movement restrictions”, “public event cancellations”. Ritchie et al. (2020) also developed a “stringency index” to measure how strict the COVID-19 policies were in different countries. The index considered the number of policies in place, whether they were recommendations or requirements, and if they were specific or general. In this study, we adopted this “stringency index” to analyse the evolution of the index throughout the month of March. We classified the countries into three groups based on their index values: those with values below or equal to 10 were labelled as having no lockdown measures, those with values between 10 and 70 were designated as having partial measures, and those with values above 70 were identified as implementing full lockdown measures. **Figure 1** provides an illustration of the agent properties and outcomes considered in the model.

Figure 1 A brief overview of the ABM model

2.2. Model Description

The model is a Python-MESA implementation of a data-driven agent-based model, with its central concept revolving around the diffusion of lockdown policies among countries. The primary mechanism of diffusion posits that countries observe the adoption of lockdowns by other nations, and if those nations share sufficient similarities, they are inclined to adopt similar lockdown measures. In simpler terms, countries tend to mimic the actions of similar countries. The model simplifies by attributing to agents (countries) the adoption of one of three measures based on the stringency index: "no lockdown," "partial lockdown," and "full lockdown." The model comprises of 164 agents, corresponding to the number of countries for which we gathered comprehensive data on the COVID policy response, along with country-specific variables like national income and level of democracy. National income is represented by the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita in Purchasing Power Parity (World Bank 2022), the degree of democracy is evaluated using the Democracy Index (DI) from the Economist Intelligence Unit (Economist Intelligence Unit 2020). Apart from the two dimensions, national income, and degree of democracy, we also considered the "covid cases per thousand population" to assess the similarity between the countries. It must be noted that there was no significant correlation between the covid-19 cases and the countries adopting partial lockdown measures (refer **Figure 1**). However, the increase in number of countries adopting strict measures was highly correlated with the increase in total covid cases across the globe. Hence, incorporating "covid cases per thousand population" (CVD) as a parameter in the model to compute the similarity index was crucial. It is noteworthy that the original form of this parameter lacked the ability to represent policy measures adopted across nations. Consequently, we performed an exponential transformation on this parameter. Following Sebhatu et al.'s (2020) findings, we introduced population density as an additional parameter. This study involved the interaction of population density with "covid cases per thousand population." This study employed an evenly weighted average across all the dimensions, normalising the values for each dimension to the unit interval [0, 1]. This similarity measure is regarded as the distance between two countries, with a lower distance indicating a higher degree of similarity between them. The distance, d_{ij} , between two countries i and j is estimated as,

$$d_{ij} = \frac{1}{3} \left(\left(\frac{e^{CVD_i} - e^{CVD_j}}{e^{CVD_{max}} - e^{CVD_{min}}} \right) * \left(\frac{Popden_i - Popden_j}{Popden_{max} - Popden_{min}} \right) + \left(\frac{GDP_i - GDP_j}{GDP_{max} - GDP_{min}} \right) + \left(\frac{DI_i - DI_j}{DI_{max} - DI_{min}} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

Figure 2 Actual and Predicted percentage of countries adopting different policy measures

2.3. Results

We utilised data from Our World in Data (Mathieu et al., 2020), which was originally compiled by the Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker team (Hale et al., 2021), for the validation and

Figure 3 Evolution in policy diffusion over the period of March 2020 based on our ABM model (a) March 1, (b) March 6, and (c) March 31

calibration of our model. We adjusted the model parameters[‡] to align the diffusion curve of national lockdowns over time (refer to **Figure 2**) with the mean outcome from an ensemble of simulations (with $N = 100$). While we aim to minimize the discrepancy between the mean prediction and the actual data, we refrain from specifying an exact loss function for this experiment, given the marginal added value of optimal calibration. Our primary goal is to have a model that reasonably captures the data before initiating our data assimilation experiments. During this phase, we assessed the fit based on the correlation between the mean prediction and the actual data. **Figure 3** illustrates the projected stringency in policy measures adopted by various countries on March 1, 16, and 31 in the year 2020.

3. Conclusion and Way Forward

The study's findings have important implications for global crisis management strategies. While Sebhatu et al's (2020) research highlighted the influence of OECD countries on each other, our analysis adds nuance by categorizing the stringency of measures and exploring their impact on the trajectory of the pandemic. Moving forward, it is crucial for policymakers to consider the effectiveness of stringent measures in controlling the spread of COVID-19. Our model provides a valuable tool for gaining insights into the impact of peer mimicry on the adoption of national lockdown measures. It must be noted from the results that the 'partial lockdown' is consistently overpredicted in our base model highlighting the nuanced dynamics of policy adoption and the inherent challenges in modeling such complex systems accurately. Therefore, it is crucial to capture the swiftness with which countries implemented policies related to lockdowns. To address this, there is a need to construct a model capable of forecasting short-term national policy changes before their actual occurrence in the future. Given the rapid pace of lockdown adoptions by countries, even minor errors in model predictions can result in simulated tipping points happening either too early or too late, leading to suboptimal model performance. To address this challenge, future research can introduce a novel methodological feature in ABMs to synchronise the model with the real system's evolution. Specifically, the incorporation of data assimilation (DA) methods can help constrain the model by regularly integrating updated observations that reflect the current state of the real-world. This approach can enhance the accuracy of future model predictions.

References

- Cuevas, E. 2020. An agent-based model to evaluate the COVID-19 transmission risks in facilities. *Computers in biology and medicine*. **121**, p.103827.
- Economist Intelligence Unit 2020. *Democracy Index 2019 A year of democratic setbacks and popular protest* [Online]. Available from: <https://www.eiu.com/topic/democracy-index>.
- Hale, T., Angrist, N., Goldszmidt, R., Kira, B., Petherick, A., Phillips, T., Webster, S., Cameron-Blake, E., Hallas, L., Majumdar, S. and Tatlow, H. 2021. A global panel database of pandemic policies (Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker). *Nature Human Behaviour*. **5**(4), pp.529–538.
- Kai, D., Goldstein, G.-P., Morgunov, A., Nangalia, V. and Rotkirch, A. 2020. Universal Masking is Urgent in the COVID-19 Pandemic: SEIR and Agent Based Models, Empirical Validation, Policy Recommendations. *arXiv preprint*. **arXiv:2004.13553**.
- Kerr, C., Stuart, R., Mistry, D., Abeyasuriya, R., Rosenfeld, K., Hart, G., Núñez, R., Cohen, J., Selvaraj, P., Hagedorn B, George L, Jastrzębski M, Izzo AS, Fowler G, Palmer A, Delport D, Scott N, Kelly SL, Bennette CS, Wagner BG, Chang ST, Oron AP, Wenger EA, Panovska-Griffiths J, Famulare M and Klein DJ. 2021. Covasim: An agent-based model of COVID-19 dynamics and interventions. *PLoS Comput Biol*. **17**(7).
- Kiesling, E., Günther, M., Stummer, C. and Wakolbinger, L.M. 2012. Agent-based simulation of innovation diffusion: a review. *Central European Journal of Operations Research*. **20**(2), pp.183–

[‡] In this context, the model parameters serve as nudge factors ensuring alignment between predicted and actual data. Lockdown adoption probability for countries ranges from 0.0002 to 0.07, with a set value of 0.01. A threshold parameter, influencing policy adoption, varies from 0.02 to 0.25, set at 0.13. Additionally, the number of peer groups shaping a country's decision on stringency is fixed at 18, varying from 10 to 25.

- Lorig, F., Johansson, E. and Davidsson, P. 2021. Agent-Based Social Simulation of the Covid-19 Pandemic: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*. **24**(3).
- Mathieu, E., Ritchie, H., Rodés-Guirao, L., Appel, C., Giattino, C., Hasell, J., Macdonald, B., Dattani, S., Beltekian, D., Ortiz-Ospina, E. and Roser, M. 2020. Coronavirus Pandemic (COVID-19). *Our World in Data*.
- Sebhatu, A., Wennberg, K., Arora-Jonsson, S. and Lindberg, S.I. 2020. Explaining the homogeneous diffusion of COVID-19 nonpharmaceutical interventions across heterogeneous countries. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. **117**(35).
- World Bank 2022. GDP, PPP (constant 2017 international \$). Available from: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.PP.KD>.

Biographies

Dr. **Jayita Chakraborty**, currently serving as a Teaching Fellow in Urban Data Science and Analytics, formerly held the position of Research Fellow in the Data Assimilation for Agent-Based Models (DUST) project. Her research focuses on utilising agent-based models and machine learning techniques to model scenarios related to on-demand services, pedestrian movements, and the diffusion of policies in global emergency situations.

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